

BIODT
biodiversitydigitaltwin

Project Title	Biodiversity Digital Twin for Advanced Modelling, Simulation and Prediction Capabilities
Project Acronym	BioDT
Project Number	101057437
Type of Project	RIA - Research and Innovation Action
Topics	HORIZON-INFRA-2021-TECH-01-01
Starting Date of Project	1 June 2022
Ending Date of Project	31 May 2025
Duration of the Project	36 months
Website	www.biodt.eu

D3.2 - Software for Digital Twin Advanced Technical Platform

Work Package	WP3 Digital Twin Advanced Technical Platform
Task	T3.1 Platform Architecture and Implementation
Lead Authors	Ilja Livenson (UTARTU), Ville Savolainen (CSC)
Contributors	Tomáš Martinovič (IT4I@VSB), Vaclav Svaton (IT4I@VSB)
Peer Reviewers	Rita Giuffrida (TRUST-IT SRL), Joaquín López Lériida (LifeWatch ERIC)
Version	V1.0
Due Date	31/05/2024
Submission Date	31/05/2024

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	SEN: Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-RES. Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-CON. Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)

Funded by
the European Union

Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	19/04/2024	Ville Savolainen (CSC)	ToC
0.2	29/04/2024	Tomáš Martinovič (IT4I@VSB)	Shiny hosting, BioDT integrations
0.3	02/05/2024	Vaclav Svaton (IT4I@VSB)	HEAppE, LEXIS inputs
0.4	03/05/2024	Ville Savolainen (CSC)	General editing, Glossary, Disclaimer
0.5	04/05/2024	Ilja Livenson (UTARTU)	Puhuri inputs, Architecture, Summary tables
0.6	06/05/2024	Ville Savolainen (CSC)	Minor editing, comments added
0.7	07/05/2024	Vaclav Svaton (IT4I@VSB)	DDI (subsection 2.4.2) added
0.8	17/05/2024	Ilja Livenson (UTARTU), Ville Savolainen (CSC), Vaclav Svaton (IT4I@VSB)	Internal review comments considered, document submitted to BioDT Project Management Board (PMB) for review
0.9	28/05/2024	Ilja Livenson (UTARTU), Vaclav Svaton (IT4I@VSB), Ville Savolainen (CSC)	Internal review comments considered
1.0	31/05/2024	Tuomas Rossi (CSC), Anna-Liisa Allas (CSC)	Submission-ready version incorporating BioDT Project Management Office (PMO) editorial changes

Glossary of Terms

Item	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
CSC	CSC – IT Center for Science Ltd
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
DDI	Distributed Data Infrastructure
DT	Digital Twin
HEAppE	High-end Application Execution Middleware
HPC	High-performance Computing
iRODS	Integrated Rule-oriented Data System
IT4I	IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center
LDAP	Lightweight Directory Access Protocol
LifeWatch ERIC	e-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research

pDT	prototype Digital Twin
REST	Representational State Transfer
RSA	Public key cryptosystem
SDK	Software Development Kit
SSSD	System Security Services Daemon
Slurm	Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management job scheduler
SSH	Secure Shell Protocol
VM	Virtual Machine

Keywords

Architecture, Artificial Intelligence, Biodiversity, Digital Twin, FAIR, High-Performance Computing, Modelling, Prediction, Simulation

Disclaimer

The BioDT project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101057437 (<https://doi.org/10.3030/101057437>). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

Executive Summary

This document describes the software components that are used for building the digital twin platform in the BioDT project and can be used for integrating new sites into the platform. Section 2 gives the overviews of the architecture, application hosting, BioDT Services and the BioDT Infrastructure Layer. Section 3 gives the overview of the licensing of the different software components. Further, the document has a vocabulary including working definitions of the key technical concepts used by the BioDT consortium.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	7
2. Components of BioDT Platform.....	7
2.1 Architecture overview	7
2.2 BioDT Application hosting	8
2.2.1 Shiny hosting	8
2.2.2 LifeWatch ERIC VR	8
2.3 BioDT services.....	8
2.3.1 BioDT allocations	8
2.3.2 BioDT Distributed Data Infrastructure Core and BioDT Workflow management and orchestrator.....	11
2.4 BioDT Infrastructure layer	14
2.4.1 HPC-as-a-Service.....	14
2.4.2 Distributed Data Infrastructure	16
2.4.3 Puhuri Agents	17
2.5 Approach to integration	18
3. Licensing	18
3.1 Overview.....	18
3.2 Summary.....	19
Reference list.....	20

List of Figures

Figure 1 – High level overview of architectural building blocks of the BioDT platform	7
Figure 2 – Overview of the Puhuri service.....	9
Figure 3 – Overview of the Waldur platform	10
Figure 4 – Waldur's and hence Puhuri Core's technology stack	10
Figure 5 – Workflow in LEXIS Portal (web-based UI).....	11
Figure 6 – Output dataset in LEXIS Portal.....	12
Figure 7 – Output dataset (list of files) in LEXIS Portal	13
Figure 8 – LEXIS sign-on	13
Figure 9 – HEAppE Middleware architecture overview	14
Figure 10 – HEAppE Middleware account mapping	15
Figure 11 – Command Templates.....	15
Figure 12 – DDI architecture scheme	17
Figure 13 – Example of an HPC site integration using reference Puhuri agents.....	18

List of Tables

Table 1 – Licensing overview	19
Table 2 – Licensing summary for the software components	20

1. Introduction

This deliverable focuses on the software components that either are used for building the BioDT platform or are used for integrating new sites into the platform. Sustainability of the services that have been built using these components and used within BioDT is in the scope of D2.4 Sustainability Report.

2. Components of BioDT Platform

2.1 Architecture overview

BioDT Platform was designed to be sustainable, extendable, and non-intrusive. For that, priority was given to platform components that are delivered as services or open-source components with a high level of maturity. The detailed description of the architecture is given in D3.1 Architecture and implementation plan. Not all of the components of the BioDT architecture are delivered using dedicated services and software components as in some cases alignment is achieved through common standards, e.g. FAIR Digital Objects. In this deliverable we concentrate on the software aspects and hence only look at the relevant parts of the platform, highlighted with green in Figure 1.

From the point of the platform, the main blocks include:

- A common set of core services represented by **BioDT services**. Exposes BioDT platform level APIs to developers.
- A set of components deployed at each HPC site represented by **BioDT Infrastructure Layer**. This layer is abstracted from the consumers by the BioDT Services platform layer.
- Consumers of the core services - applications hosted at the **BioDT Application hosting**. Typically expose end user interface and connected to BioDT services in the backend.

Figure 1 – High level overview of architectural building blocks of the BioDT platform

Green highlight is used for showing components that are delivered using specific software or services.

Below we summarise the main services and software components used to build up these blocks.

2.2 BioDT Application hosting

BioDT Application hosting represents any hosting services that is eligible and able to connect to the BioDT services. The hosting is responsibility of a specific Digital Twin operator, within the BioDT project a hosting for Digital Twins is provided using the Shiny hosting in CSC. In addition, LifeWatch ERIC is integrating platform using provided SDK for BioDT services.

2.2.1 Shiny hosting

The main point of interaction with BioDT prototype Digital Twins (pDTs) from the end user perspective will be a web application created as an R Shiny Application (<https://shiny.posit.co>) which is being developed in the WP7. This web interface will allow the user to interact either with the results of the Digital Twins, or setup and execute a computation of digital twin simulations depending on how the pDT is designed. Currently, the development version of the app is running on the CSC Pouta cluster on an OpenStack (<https://www.openstack.org>) VM, using ShinyProxy (<https://www.shinyproxy.io>) to serve the application as an individual container to the users. This assures scalability and containerized environment for individual users.

The CSC team in WP7 is working on transferring this setup to the CSC Rahti cluster running Red Hat OpenShift (<https://www.redhat.com/en/technologies/cloud-computing/openshift>). This will increase efficiency since it does not need to run the VM all the time and will spawn the pods only when the applications are used.

2.2.2 LifeWatch ERIC VR

The integration of the workflow execution service of BioDT is going to be made in My LifeWatch platform (<https://my.lifewatch.eu>). This work will leverage py4lexis to interact with LEXIS workflows and make them executable from the LifeWatch ERIC VR platform, increasing the potential reach of BioDT. The exact details of how this will work are still being discussed. This integration with LifeWatch ERIC is briefly discussed in D7.1 First Stage Community Platform Integration Report.

2.3 BioDT services

Base BioDT services are provided centrally by the BioDT project for the Digital Twins and expose a coherent platform for developing and running Digital Twins. They are based on the three components:

- **BioDT Allocations**, based on Puhuri Core, which in turn is built on the Waldur platform - service providing sharing and management of resources from resource allocators to different HPC sites;
- **BioDT Distributed Data Infrastructure Core** and **BioDT Workflow management and orchestrator** based on the LEXIS platform, providing workflow orchestration and data management over multiple set of HPC sites.

While these services are provided as managed services with BioDT, we describe below their setup from the building blocks.

2.3.1 BioDT allocations

BioDT Allocations connect computational and storage allocations from resource allocators, for example, EuroHPC JU or national service providers, with the infrastructure sites. In BioDT, we picked Puhuri service (<https://puhuri.neic.no/>) for delivering such a functionality.

2.3.1.1 Puhuri platform

The Puhuri platform is a set of integrated services for managing access to shared resources in a federated manner. This site aims to provide high-level technical information about Puhuri service for target stakeholders. In turn, Puhuri service (see Figure 2) contains several parts, from the point of integration the

more important is Puhuri Core, based on an open-source Waldur platform (<https://docs.waldur.com/>). The latter was extended to provide a more seamless integration with the LEXIS platform.

Puhuri is using Geant's MyAccessID AAI¹ for user registration that can be started from National Portal of Resource Allocators or from Puhuri Portal, which is provided as a reference solution. The registration process creates a unique identifier (Community Unique Identifier, CUID) for the user, which is used for referencing and linking user identity across the different components.

The identity provider releases the attributes about User's identity and affiliation, which is important for the resource providers to know. User can also register SSH public keys for easier access to the Linux-based systems that are accessible in Puhuri. For BioDT, in addition to the support of user keys, robot accounts have been developed in a way conformant to hosting site security requirements that allowed to create a fully automated account setup for the LEXIS projects.

Puhuri Core is an API service² for Resource Allocators that allows to manage Projects, Members (using CUID of Puhuri users) as well as Resource Allocations. A Resource provider then imports the allocation and project membership information from the Puhuri Core and sets up the services for access using MyAccessID user account or robot accounts for that allocation. Resource provider also reports on the usage of resource allocations as well as provides additional data, like Linux usernames, that user might need in order to access the Resource.

Puhuri Core has an offline access to MyAccessID user registry and uses it for keeping user information up to date.

Figure 2 – Overview of the Puhuri service

Connection between Puhuri Core and HPC sites is depicted with an arrow at the bottom.

¹ <https://wiki.geant.org/display/MyAccessID/MyAccessID+Home>

² <https://puhuri.neic.no/resource-allocators/> - description of Puhuri Core APIs
<https://www.biodt.eu/>

2.3.1.2 Waldur platform

Waldur is a platform for managing hybrid cloud resources (see Figure 3). It is used both for controlling internal enterprise IT resources and for selling cloud services. Waldur is composed of the following main components:

- Waldur MasterMind - broker and orchestrator of cloud services. Responsible for technical service delivery and connected matters. Exposes REST API for management.
- Waldur HomePort - web-based self-service portal. Talks REST to MasterMind.

Figure 3 – Overview of the Waldur platform

In Puhuri, it serves as Puhuri Core connecting HPC sites in a common fashion with resource allocators and end-users.

On the technical side, Waldur is built on fully open-source stack of technologies (see Figure 4):

- Homeport (web client, graphical interface) - React application
- Mastermind API server - Django/Django REST Framework application implementing the core business logic
- Celery workers - Background processing of tasks
- Celery beat - Scheduling of periodic tasks for background processing
- PostgreSQL database - Storing persistent data, also serves as Celery result store in Kubernetes deployment
- Redis - Tasks queue and result store for Celery (Docker Compose deployment only)
- RabbitMQ - Tasks queue and result store for Celery (Kubernetes deployment only)

Figure 4 – Waldur's and hence Puhuri Core's technology stack

2.3.2 BioDT Distributed Data Infrastructure Core and BioDT Workflow management and orchestrator

BioDT Distributed Data Infrastructure Core and BioDT Workflow management and orchestrator are delivered through the LEXIS platform. It is a complex system providing to the end-users the possibility to use the HPC and Cloud infrastructure at a full scale. The platform is equipped with services for complex computing workflow orchestration and distributed data management over the HPC centers connected to the platform. Multiple HPC resources are (easily and uniquely) accessible via API and web-based user interface. The orchestrator used by the platform is based on Apache Airflow [1]. Each workflow is defined as a Python file and is represented as a directed acyclic graph (DAG). The platform also provides the possibility to define a workflow using YAML description based on TOSCA standard [2]. The workflows can consist of various dependent tasks that trigger and monitor data movement, Kubernetes container and HPC batch job operations (see Figure 5). The Apache Airflow has a concept of DAG runs. The given concept can be seen as instances of a particular workflow with a set of parameters defined at the beginning of the execution. In this manner, the executions of the same workflow with various parameter values can be tracked in a unified way.

Figure 5 – Workflow in LEXIS Portal (web-based UI)

The LEXIS Platform defines an abstraction to work with different compute projects, user groups, and resource allocations. The basic element of the platform is a LEXIS Project, which has its own set of users with various associated roles and a set of resource allocations. Each project has its own datasets, workflows, and users. The resource abstraction is used by an HPC-as-a-Service middleware called HEAppE (described in Section 2.4.1) deployed near each connected HPC cluster to manage credentials and access to the HPC applications through HEAppE Command Templates. These templates are essentially parametrised job scripts used to launch only a precisely defined set of commands on the clusters through the HEAppE API which is used by the LEXIS Orchestrator. In this way, the user is completely isolated from the cluster-specific configuration and does not have a possibility to directly access the executable files of the application. Technical details of this implementation can be found in [3].

2.3.2.1 Distributed Data Infrastructure (DDI)

The Distributed Data Interface (DDI) ensures data movement capabilities within the LEXIS Platform. It contains methods used for data transfer between the user and a target site, as well as staging features for moving data to and from HPC clusters and other compute resources. For example, the data transfers between locations use native iRODS³ protocol, which leverages parallel TCP streams, native POSIX protocols common in the HPC environment such as SFTP or RSync and HTTPS chunked transfers for web-based front ends or similar clients. User data in the DDI are encapsulated into the datasets which is like a classical directory represented as iRODS collections. Each dataset can have a rich set of user defined metadata [4] (see Figure 6). These metadata are indexed in a centralised ElasticSearch⁴ index and at the same time in iRODS instance located in the datacentre (iRODS zones). It is typical that each HPC site is hosting its own iRODS zone. The DDI then uses a set of custom-built APIs and asynchronous worker processes which perform the actual data movement using native protocols.

The screenshot shows a web interface for a dataset. At the top, there is a breadcrumb trail: Home > Workflow DataSets > TOSCA AIRFLOW test output > Details. Below this is a toolbar with buttons for Copy Id, Copy Path, File List, Delete, and Download. The main content area is titled 'TOSCA AIRFLOW test output' and 'Details'. It contains two columns of metadata:

Data Set Access Mode:	project	Data Creation Date:	25th of Apr 2024
Project:	testproject	Data Creator(s):	TOSCA TEST
Zone:	IT4ILexisV2	Encryption:	no
Data Set Owner(s):	TOSCA TEST	Compression:	no

Figure 6 – Output dataset in LEXIS Portal

The workflows then use the DDI capabilities to perform dataset movement to a target location. It can be also used to store the resulting dataset (from, e.g., an HPC job - see Figure 7) with the necessary metadata. Within the DDI, the following accesses to the datasets are recognized:

- *user* – datasets are visible only by a particular user in a given LEXIS Project;
- *project* – shared among all project users;
- *public* – available to all logged-in users of the LEXIS Platform.

Each site used in execution has an HEAppE Middleware and a DDI worker process deployed (usually on a virtual machine). The HEAppE is used apart from the HPC job management also for data transfer credentials management by the DDI worker process.

³ iRODS official website: <https://irods.org/>

⁴ <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch> - a distributed, RESTful search and analytics engine

Figure 7 – Output dataset (list of files) in LEXIS Portal

2.3.2.2 Single Sign-On Concept / AAI

Users are internally managed via a LEXIS AAI, which is based on Keycloak [5] and is federated with external identity providers such as B2ACCESS [6] and MyAccessID [7] (see Figure 8). After sign-on, authentication is managed with tokens (with authentication flows based on OpenID-Connect [8]). Given authentication approach is used for the LEXIS Portal (web-based user interface – <https://portal.lexis.tech>), as well as for the Py4Lexis Python package (<https://opencode.it4i.eu/lexis-platform/clients/py4lexis>) which provides Python based API for the LEXIS Platform.

Figure 8 – LEXIS sign-on

2.3.2.3 Extensibility of the LEXIS Platform

The ambition of the LEXIS Platform includes the possibility to integrate further computing and data centers or to federate with them. This involves, as necessary, adapters to systems beyond those addressed with the initial LEXIS Platform.

2.4 BioDT Infrastructure layer

BioDT Infrastructure layer is intended to be deployed next to the HPC site's service and provide a common interface for integration with an HPC site. It is intended to be lightweight and non-intrusive to simplify on-boarding of new HPC sites to BioDT platform. The main components are:

- HEAppE middleware connecting to the specific hardware scheduler in HPC site, e.g., SLURM or Kubernetes.
- DDI component that manages input, output and intermediate data for computing, and related metadata utilizing iRODS and ElasticSearch.
- Puhuri agents interacting with HPC site's local allocations service.

2.4.1 HPC-as-a-Service

High-End Application Execution Middleware (HEAppE Middleware) is IT4I's in-house implementation of the HPC-as-a-Service concept. HPC-as-a-Service concept in high-performance computing focuses on technologies that enable users remote and secure access to an HPC infrastructure without the need to manage their own physical servers or data center infrastructure.

HEAppE Middleware (see Figure 9) provides simple and intuitive REST API access to the supercomputing infrastructure. This framework is utilizing a mid-layer principle, in software terminology also known as middleware. Middleware manages and provides information about submitted and running jobs and their data between the client application and the HPC infrastructure. HEAppE can submit required computation or simulation on the HPC infrastructure and monitor the progress of the jobs. It provides all the necessary functions for job management, monitoring and reporting, user authentication and authorization, file transfer between user and HPC, encryption, and various notification mechanisms.

Figure 9 – HEAppE Middleware architecture overview

2.4.1.1 HEAppE Middleware account mapping

HEAppE Middleware performs the mapping of the external users to functional (non-privileged) accounts for the HPC infrastructure (see Figure 10). Due to the security-critical functionality, it is recommended for HEAppE to be deployed in an HPC center's private network. The external user accounts are saved in the HEAppE Middleware instance database, whereas internal accounts are stored in an SSH Agent instance/HashiCorp Vault (Vault support is currently tested as a part of the new pre-release version of

HEAppE). The Primary Investigator (PI) of each computational project is responsible for adding internal cluster accounts into the specific SSH Agent instance/Vault (run separately for each project).

Figure 10 – HEAppE Middleware account mapping

2.4.1.2 Command Templates

For security purposes HEAppE enables the users to run only pre-prepared set of so-called Command Templates (see Figure 11). Each template defines arbitrary script or executable file that will be executed on the cluster, any dependencies or third-party software it might require and the specific queue that should be used for the processing (type of computing nodes to be used on the cluster). The template also contains the set of input parameters that will be passed to the executable script during run-time. Thus, the users are only able to execute pre-prepared command templates with the pre-defined set of input parameters. The actual value of each parameter (input from the user) can be changed by the user for each job submission.

Figure 11 – Command Templates

2.4.1.3 HEAppE Middleware SSH key generation and robot accounts

Within the integration of HEAppE Middleware in the BioDT project, the functionality of HEAppE has been extended to include the capability of generating an SSH key pair for a robot account. From the perspective of HEAppE, a robot account is an internal cluster account created and utilized for communication with HPC infrastructure. Thanks to this extension, HEAppE can generate an SSH key pair, which it internally assigns to

the computational project, and this account will be used for communication with the HPC infrastructure. Upon key generation, HEAppE provides the public part of the SSH key to Puhuri service, while the encrypted private key remains within the HEAppE Middleware and is ready for use after propagating the SSH key to the HPC infrastructure, which is handled by the Puhuri service. This HEAppE feature also provides ability to regenerate the selected key and to remove and unlink the key from the computational project.

Furthermore, this functionality enhances the usability of HEAppE and ensures a more secure process of SSH keys management by eliminating the manual admin-user manipulation with the private key, which remains under the control of HEAppE. During the configuration of HEAppE Middleware, it is additionally possible to specify the type and length of the generated SSH keys. Currently, HEAppE can generate encrypted SSH keys using the RSA algorithm with key lengths of 3072 or 4096, as well as ECDSA keys utilizing elliptic curves of type nistP256 or nistP521. This provides flexibility in tailoring the security measures according to specific project requirements.

2.4.1.4 HEAppE Middleware license and maturity

HEAppE Middleware is licensed under the GNU General Public License v3. The development of this framework started more than 10 years ago when it was apparent that there is a growing community of users that wants to integrate HPC capabilities in their own solutions or just need a simple interface to utilize the power of supercomputers within their specific domains. Since then HEAppE Middleware has been successfully integrated into a number of national and international projects under the header of Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe, and European Space Agency projects and many others and also deployed at several major HPC infrastructure or data center providers throughout Europe. See <http://heappe.eu>.

2.4.2 Distributed Data Infrastructure

To be able to utilize DDI's features the so-called Staging worker needs to be in place at each respective site. The staging worker is an instance of a Celery⁵ worker that is connected to the central PostgreSQL and RabbitMQ instances and executes the actual tasks which access the data and performs the requested operations (see Figure 12). Each location has its own unique queue and can deploy multiple workers, according to the scalability requirements. Triggering of the tasks and their submission to queues is handled in the Staging API Django application.

The staging worker supports the following data transfer protocols: - Direct POSIX access (staging area) - Rsync/SFTP for HPC clusters - iRODS zones/federation - S3/Swift object storages (planned) - Relational and document databases (planned). These workers are implemented in the same way as the staging worker - as a Celery process, allowing the same scaling capability. The compression worker leverages parallel gzip implementation, which in combination with fast flash-based storage for staging area offers fast compression or decompression of extensive datasets. Thanks to the modular nature of the Celery workers, more compression methods can be added.

The encryption worker handles symmetric encryption of the datasets using OpenSSL and hardware accelerated (where available) AES-256 algorithm. The keys are handled automatically within the platform for each encryption and decryption operations.

Staging worker also leverages HEAppE's REST API access to HPC cluster storage to provide remote access to a compute job directory to prepare the input data there to be ready for the job execution.

⁵ <https://github.com/celery/celery> - a distributed task queue engine
<https://www.biodt.eu/>

Figure 12 – DDI architecture scheme

The data transfer API handles the upload and download of the datasets in the LEXIS Platform including their metadata. This API is used for chunked HTTPS-based upload implemented by the TUS protocol and HTTPS-based download of the dataset's contents. It leverages the staging and metadata APIs for its operation.

2.4.3 Puhuri Agents

To connect HPC site to Puhuri to allow federated allocation management in BioDT, the following functionalities need to be fulfilled:

- Mapping of global identities from MyAccessID to local site identities;
- Propagation of local identities to computational nodes if required by the system (e.g., SLURM scheduler, a popular scheduler for batch services provided by supercomputing sites);
- Propagation of allocation information (limits and membership) from Puhuri to HPC site and usage from HPC site to Puhuri.

Puhuri's design is non-intrusive and leaves sites with flexibility of creating their own integrations, which was the case for EuroHPC LUMI, or to use open-source components for achieving the functionality. The following agents are provided as reference (see Figure 13):

- KeyCloak proxy acting as Site Identity Proxy connected to MyAccessID for OIDC-based access to HPC site's services.
- Service Offering user directory - a GLAuth (<https://glauth.github.io/>)-based microservice exposing an Lightweight Directory Access Protocol (LDAP) interface with user and group information of users within Puhuri allocations for a specific site. Keeps information up-to-date based on the sync process with Puhuri Core. Can be used to integrate directly with site's System Security Services Daemon (SSSD) services - a popular method of accessing remote user directory services on Linux servers.
- Waldur-slurm-agent supporting push and pull modes that interacts with SLURM scheduler and injects accounts and associations from one side and collects and reports usage information from the other.

Figure 13 – Example of an HPC site integration using reference Puhuri agents

2.5 Approach to integration

A common issue for sustainability of the services deployed for a specific project is handling of the integration code for different components. Within the BioDT, our approach for sustaining the developed integrations - most importantly of BioDT Services - was publishing extensions required for integrations as part of the upstream software component, for example, LEXIS, Heappe or Waldur. Such an approach allows to reduce the risk of the integration becoming obsolete and simplifies potential adoption or deployment of systems similar to BioDT. The latter is achievable as partners within WP3 are also contributing to the development of the corresponding software projects. Hence developed extensions required for the integration became part of the external services that BioDT relies upon.

3. Licensing

3.1 Overview

BioDT platform was designed to rely on open-source and mature components to ease its fit for use cases and to reduce potential operational expenses for the operator. The licenses differ in how they affect usage, distribution and modification of software components as summarized below. See the licences directly for their exact, detailed conditions.

License	Meaning	Use	Distribution	Modification
MIT	A permissive license allowing users to do almost anything with the code as long as the original	Can use the code for any purpose, including commercial use.	Can distribute the code in original or modified form.	Can modify the code and distribute it under the same

	license and copyright notice are included.			license or a compatible one.
GPLv3	A copyleft license that requires derivative works to be licensed under the same terms, ensuring that the source code remains open and freely available.	Can use the code for any purpose, including commercial use.	Can distribute the code, but derivative works must be under GPLv3.	Can modify the code, but derivative works must be under GPLv3.
Apache 2.0	A permissive license with additional terms that grant users rights to patents that cover the code, and includes an express grant of patent rights from contributors.	Can use the code for any purpose, including commercial use.	Can distribute the code in original or modified form.	Can modify the code and distribute it under the same license or a compatible one.
BSD 3-Clause	A permissive license similar to the MIT license, but with an additional clause preventing the use of the name of the project or its contributors to endorse derived products.	Can use the code for any purpose, including commercial use.	Can distribute the code in original or modified form.	Can modify the code and distribute it under the same license or a compatible one.
Business Source License	A hybrid license that starts as a proprietary license and then converts to an open source license after a defined period or when certain conditions are met.	Limited use during the proprietary period, full use after conversion.	Can distribute the code under the proprietary terms or after conversion.	Can modify the code, but during the proprietary period, modifications must be shared.

Table 1 – Licensing overview

3.2 Summary

Below we provide a licensing summary for the software components used in the BioDT platform.

Software	Component	BioDT layer	License	Code
Shiny	BioDT Application hosting	BioDT Application hosting	GPLv3	https://github.com/rstudio/shiny
Waldur	BioDT Allocations	BioDT Services	MIT	https://github.com/waldur
LEXIS	BioDT Workflow management and orchestrator	BioDT Services	Apache2 / MIT	https://opencode.it4i.eu/lexis-platform
iRODS	BioDT Distributed Data	BioDT Services	3-clause BSD License	https://github.com/irods/irods

	Infrastructure Core			
HEAppE	HPC-as-a-Service	BioDT Infrastructure Layer	GPLv3	https://github.com/lt4innovations/HEAppE
Waldur-slurm-service	Puhuri agent	BioDT Infrastructure Layer	MIT	https://github.com/waldur/waldur-slurm-service
GLAuth	Puhuri agent	BioDT Infrastructure Layer	MIT	https://github.com/waldur/glauth
KeyCloak	Puhuri agent	BioDT Infrastructure Layer	Apache2	https://github.com/keycloak/keycloak
Hashicorp Vault	HPC-as-a-Service	BioDT Infrastructure Layer	Business Source License	https://github.com/hashicorp/vault
py4lexis	BioDT Application hosting	BioDT Application hosting	MIT	https://opencode.it4i.eu/lexis-platform/clients/py4lexis

Table 2 – Licensing summary for the software components

Reference list

1. Harenslak, B., de Ruiter, J., 2021. Data Pipelines with Apache Airflow. Manning Publications. ISBN: 9781617296901.
2. OASIS, 2020. Tosca simple profile in yaml version 1.3. URL: <https://docs.oasis-open.org/tosca/TOSCA-Simple-Profile-YAML/v1.3/TOSCA-Simple-Profile-YAML-v1.3.pdf>.
3. Golasowski, M., Martinovič, J., Křenek, J., Slaninová, K., Levrier, M., Harsh, P., Derquennes, M., Donnat, F., Terzo, O., 2022. The lexis platform for distributed workflow execution and data management, in: HPC, Big Data, and AI Convergence Towards Exascale. Taylor & Francis.
4. Munke, J., Hayek, M., Golasowski, M., García-Hernández, R.J., Donnat, F., Koch-Hofer, C., Couvee, P., Hachinger, S., Martinovič, J., 2022. Chapter 4 Data System and Data Management in a Federation of HPC/Cloud Centers. Taylor & Francis.
5. Keycloak Community: Keycloak., 2024. Available: <https://www.keycloak.org>.
6. EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure: B2ACCESS - EUDAT, 2023. Available: <https://www.eudat.eu/catalogue/b2access>.
7. GÉANT Association: MyAccessID Home - MyAccessID - GÉANT federated confluence, 2024. Available: <https://wiki.geant.org/display/MyAccessID/MyAccessID+Home>.
8. N. Sakimura, J. Bradley, M. Jones, B. De Medeiros, and C. Mortimore, "Openid connect core 1.0," The OpenID Foundation, pp. S3, 2014. Available: https://openid.net/specs/openid-connect-core-1_0.html.